

The Selection Process

General string

((“conversational agent” OR chatbot OR “chat bot” OR chatterbot OR “dialogue system” OR “pedagogical agent” OR “virtual agent” OR “virtual assistant”) AND (education OR learn OR pedagogic OR teach)).

Adaptation of the string to the search bases:

ACM Digital Library

Searched for (("conversational agent" OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR "pedagogical agent" OR "virtual agent" OR "dialogue system" OR "virtual assistant") AND (education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic))

- Expand your search to The ACM Guide to Computing Literature

Elsevier (Science Direct)

pub-date > 2006 and TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("conversational agent" OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR "pedagogical agent" OR "virtual agent" OR "dialogue system" OR "virtual assistant" OR "chat bot") and TITLE-ABSTR-KEY(education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic).

Engineering Village

((“conversational agent” OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR “pedagogical agent” OR “virtual agent” OR “dialogue system” OR “virtual assistant”) AND (education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic))

IEEE Xplore

((“conversational agent” OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR “pedagogical agent” OR “virtual agent” OR “dialogue system” OR “virtual assistant” OR “chat bot”) AND (education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic))

SCOPUS

TITLE-ABS-KEY (("conversational agent" OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR "pedagogical agent" OR "virtual agent" OR "dialogue system" OR "virtual assistant" OR "chat bot") AND (education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic)) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2012) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2011) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2010) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2009) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2008) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2007))

Web of Science

TS = (("conversational agent" OR chatbot OR chatterbot OR "pedagogical agent" OR "virtual agent" OR "dialogue system" OR "virtual assistant") AND (education OR teaching OR learning OR learn OR teach OR educational OR pedagogical OR pedagogic))

- Índices=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCIS, CPCI-SSH, ESCI Tempo estipulado=2007-2017

Search date: 12-04-2018

Search summary:

Search bases	Results
ACM Digital Library	982
Elsevier (Science Direct)	129
Engineering Village	1065
IEEE Xplore	278
Scopus	2087
Web of Science	534
Total	5075

The list of returned studies is available at: <<https://bit.ly/2Ai2rtN>>.

Identification and removal of duplicate studies:

2463 duplicate studies were identified. The following table shows the total number of duplicate studies for each search base, which were identified with the support of the Parsif.al tool¹.

Search bases	Initial search	Removed	Results
ACM Digital Library	982	678	304
Elsevier (Science Direct)	129	76	53
Engineering Village	1065	464	601
IEEE Xplore	278	152	126
Scopus	2087	657	1430
Web of Science	534	429	105
Total	5075	2456	2619

¹ <https://parsif.al/>

The list of removed studies is available at: <<https://bit.ly/3dlTe1V>>.

The list containing information on the 2619 studies is available at: <<https://bit.ly/2Mf7k9J>>.

Reading of title, abstract and keywords:

The title, abstract and keywords of the 2619 studies were read. While reading these studies, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered. In total, 2071 studies were removed.

Selection criteria	Number of studies removed
EC-1	271
EC-2	4
EC-3	57
EC-4	1739
Total	2071

The complete list of studies with their respective justification for exclusion is available at: <<https://bit.ly/2XhGdB5>>.

The following table shows the total number of studies removed by search base after reading the title, abstract and keywords, and applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Search bases	Initial search	Removed	Results
ACM Digital Library	304	258	46
Elsevier (Science Direct)	53	40	13
Engineering Village	601	460	141
IEEE Xplore	126	107	19
Scopus	1430	1134	296
Web of Science	105	72	33
Total	2619	2071	548

Reading the studies in full-text:

The remaining 548 studies were read in full and the selection criteria were applied again. In total, 447 studies were removed.

Selection criteria	Number of studies removed
EC-1	16
EC-2	2
EC-3	0
EC-4	429
Total	447

The complete list of studies with their respective justification for exclusion is available at: <https://bit.ly/36NhUhr>.

Search bases	Initial search	Removed	Results
ACM Digital Library	46	37	9
Elsevier (Science Direct)	13	11	2
Engineering Village	141	104	37
IEEE Xplore	19	12	7
Scopus	296	258	38
Web of Science	33	25	8
Total	548	447	101

The final list of primary studies that were considered for data extraction is available at: <https://bit.ly/3cjbhVh>.